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Translating across borders: Collaboration between the German online magazine *Demokratischer Salon* and Ukrainian student translators

Abstract

This article presents a qualitative case study of a long-term academia–media partnership between the German online magazine *Demokratischer Salon* and Ukrainian student translators at Mykhailo Dragomanov State University of Ukraine. The collaboration focuses on the translation of journalistic, essayistic, and popular-science texts from German into Ukrainian for publication in Ukrainian media. Drawing on published translations, student drafts, editorial communication, and the circulation of translated texts, the article examines how publication-oriented student translation can function as professional training, civic education, intercultural dialogue, and community-building. The case shows that translation in this setting creates sustained interaction among students, the supervisor, editors, authors, and readers, and gives translators practical experience of public responsibility. The article discusses the reciprocal dimension of the partnership, as *Demokratischer Salon* publishes texts connected with Ukraine for German-speaking readers.

The study argues that collaborative student translation projects can become sustainable forms of intercultural professional cooperation and civic engagement.

Keywords: student translation, translator training, public discourse, community of practice, German–Ukrainian translation, civic translation, publication-oriented pedagogy

1. Introduction

Translation becomes especially visible when public discourse crosses linguistic, political, and cultural borders. Under the conditions of Russia’s full-scale invasion of Ukraine, the circulation of texts between Ukrainian and German-speaking publics has acquired particular urgency, especially given Germany’s extensive military, civilian, financial, humanitarian, and diplomatic support for Ukraine (Federal Foreign Office 2026). Journalistic essays, interviews, reviews, and cultural commentaries shape perceptions of war, democracy, memory, responsibility, culture, and solidarity. In this context, translator education can become a form of public engagement.

This article examines a long-term collaboration between the German online magazine *Demokratischer Salon* and Ukrainian student translators at Mykhailo Dragomanov State University of Ukraine in Kyiv. The partnership began in March 2023 with the Ukrainian translation of Ursula Stark Urrestarazu’s review of Stanislav Aseyev’s personal account of imprisonment and torture at the former Izolyatsia factory in occupied Donetsk (Stark

Urrestarazu 2023a). It subsequently developed into a sustained publication-oriented translation program in which German-language essays and interviews from *Demokratischer Salon* were translated into Ukrainian, revised under academic supervision, and published in Ukrainian online venues: most prominently *Experiment*, a cultural portal, as well as *Krytyka*, an established intellectual journal, and *Syg.ma*, a multilingual community-run media platform. By May 2026, the Ukrainian side of the collaboration included 33 long-form translations: 22 essays and 11 interviews. The texts cover the Russo-Ukrainian War, peace politics, democracy, law, asylum, pedagogy, childhood, historical memory, East Germany, science fiction, solarpunk, artificial intelligence, gender, queer writing, art, music, Georgian-German cultural exchange, and Russian émigré culture in Germany.

The collaboration is coordinated through the student research-and-practice circle *Practice of Written Translation in Action*, which provides the educational framework for the work. Students translate texts from German into Ukrainian, discuss and revise their drafts, communicate with editors and authors when needed, and prepare their translations for publication. This process introduces them to professional editorial standards and gives them the experience of having their names attached to public texts. At the same time, *Demokratischer Salon* has published texts connected with Ukraine for German-speaking readers, including texts on Ukrainian theater, culture, history, German Studies in Ukraine, contemporary art, and the Russo-Ukrainian War. The partnership, therefore, has a reciprocal dimension:

German-language debates become available to Ukrainian readers, while Ukrainian cultural and intellectual debates reach German-speaking audiences.

The article asks: How does publication-oriented student translation organized through an academia–media partnership reshape translator training and intercultural cooperation under wartime conditions? To answer this question, the article analyzes the collaboration as a qualitative case study. The material consists of published translations, student drafts, editorial communication, public paratexts, and documented examples of circulation and reception. The study focuses on the social, educational, and institutional conditions that make such translation possible.

The main argument is that the partnership with *Demokratischer Salon* demonstrates how student translation can become a sustainable form of intercultural professional cooperation. It connects several groups: students, their supervisor, Ukrainian editors, German authors, Norbert Reichel as editor of *Demokratischer Salon*, and readers in different linguistic publics. Translation in this setting builds trust, creates community, supports public discourse, and gives students a practical sense of professional agency. The case also suggests that translator education benefits from authentic publication contexts, especially when students work with socially significant texts and see their work enter public circulation.

2. Translation, agency, and public responsibility

The case discussed in this article belongs to a broader set of questions in Translation Studies concerning agency, public discourse, activist translation, and situated translator training. Translation is an interpretive and social practice carried out by agents who work within institutions, media environments, political conditions, and ethical constraints. Venuti's (1995) critique of translator invisibility remains relevant, as publication contexts can still obscure translators' labor. Student translation projects can counteract this invisibility when translators are publicly credited and when the process of revision, mediation, and editorial dialogue is treated as part of professional training.

Research on translator agency has shown that translators act within networks of constraints and possibilities rather than as isolated individuals. Kinnunen and Koskinen (2010) define translators' agency through the choices translators make in specific social settings, while Wolf and Fukari (2007) place translation within broader sociological frameworks. Chesterman's (2009) proposal of Translator Studies is also relevant here because the case foregrounds translators as situated actors whose motivations, responsibilities, and professional identities deserve analysis. The students in the present case are emerging translators who negotiate source texts, editorial expectations, target readerships, and their own developing professional identities.

The war-related context also connects the case to research on translation, conflict, and activism. Baker (2018) has argued that translation

participates in the circulation of narratives, including narratives of conflict. Tymoczko (2007, 2010) has similarly shown that translators can intervene in cultural and political life by making particular voices, memories, and forms of knowledge available across languages. The translations discussed here can be described as civic because they make social, cultural, and political reflection accessible to readers across borders and help sustain informed public discourse during war.

The educational dimension of the case can be understood through project-based and situated approaches to translator training. Kiraly (2000) argues for socially grounded translator education in which students learn through authentic collaborative tasks. Koskinen and Kuusi's (2017) work on translator training for language activists is also relevant because it links translator education with agency and empowerment. Lave and Wenger's (1991) idea of situated learning and Wenger's (1998) concept of communities of practice are useful because the students gradually move from classroom participation toward membership in a wider professional community. They work with the supervisor, editors, and authors; they revise texts for publication; they translate for readers; they learn that translation decisions have consequences. Gile's (2004) work on problem and decision reporting is also relevant because the translation process requires students to identify problems, justify choices, and reflect on alternatives. Mossop's (2014) diary-based approach to motivation in translation services further reminds us that

professional translation involves emotional, institutional, and motivational factors.

This article builds on these discussions and on previous work on popular text translation in educational practice and student group translation as a cultural and educational practice (Shopin 2025b, 2025c) but shifts the focus to a concrete academia–media partnership. The central issue is how translator education changes when publication is the goal. The students work with texts intended for publication, collaborate with editors, and translate with readers in mind. Their translations enter public archives and become part of ongoing cultural exchange. Such work gives translator training a civic dimension because it links linguistic skill to public responsibility.

3. Materials and method

The study uses a qualitative, reflexive case-study design. The case is the collaboration between *Demokratischer Salon* and student translators at Mykhailo Dragomanov State University of Ukraine from March 2023 to May 2026. The material includes: (a) published Ukrainian translations of texts from *Demokratischer Salon*; (b) student drafts and revised versions; (c) editorial communication with Ukrainian and German partners; (d) public information on the *Demokratischer Salon* website; (e) related German-language publications in *Demokratischer Salon* connected with Ukraine; and (f) the supervisor’s own German translations and self-translation published in *Demokratischer Salon*.

The core Ukrainian corpus consists of 33 long-form translations from German into Ukrainian. These published translations are treated here as primary sources and are therefore included in the reference list. These were prepared by students individually or collaboratively under supervision and published mainly in *Experiment*, with one early publication in *Krytyka* and one publication in *Syg.ma*. The corpus includes essays, interviews, book reviews, exhibition-related texts, and cultural reviews. Its authors include Ursula Stark Urrestarazu, Norbert Reichel, Markus Meckel, Paul Schäfer, Fritz Heidorn, Alessandra Reiß, Zara Zerbe, Dilek Güngör, Meltem Kulaçatan, Aiki Mira, Christina Morina, Cristina Colao, Álvaro Solar, Ana Margvelashvili, Michael Hänel, Martina Winkler, Clara Marz, Karlheinz Steinmüller, and others. The texts are thematically diverse and cannot be reduced to one discipline or genre.

The article also considers the reciprocal dimension of the partnership. *Demokratischer Salon* has published texts about Ukraine and Ukrainian culture for German-speaking readers, including texts on Ukrainian theater, cultural history, literary reception, Ukrainian German Studies, and the Russo-Ukrainian War. Some of these texts were translated by Norbert Reichel from English versions. In 2025–2026, the supervisor's own contribution to this direction included seven German-language publications in *Demokratischer Salon*: one self-translation and six translations from Ukrainian into German. These reciprocal publications are discussed in Section 9 as part of the wider Ukrainian-German circulation created by the partnership.

The method is qualitative and interpretive. The study analyzes the collaboration through four connected questions: who participates in the translation process; how the workflow is organized; what kinds of texts and topics enter circulation; and what educational and civic effects the collaboration produces. The analysis relies primarily on publicly available published translations and publicly accessible paratexts. Unpublished drafts and private correspondence are not quoted; they are used only to reconstruct the workflow and the kinds of interaction that shaped the translations. Student translators are mentioned only where their names already appear in public publications. This ethical limitation follows from the article's main aim: to analyze a public educational practice.

The preserved drafts are especially useful because many collaborative projects were prepared in Google Docs. This format allowed students to comment on one another's fragments, suggest alternative solutions, and discuss difficult points before the supervisor reviewed and edited the whole text. The preserved draft history and published versions also make it possible to compare preliminary solutions with final translations and to identify recurrent or especially instructive translation problems. In the present article, such draft material is used selectively and only to illustrate the learning process. The analysis also draws on previously published questionnaire data from one documented Demokratischer Salon translation mini-project, in which students reflected on peer review, publication, language learning, and collaboration (Shopin 2025d). The discussion of circulation and reception

also draws on publicly visible traces of readership, including page-view counters on Ukrainian publication platforms, social-media sharing, comments and reactions, and correspondence in which authors responded to the Ukrainian translations. These indicators are treated as partial evidence of circulation rather than as a full measure of impact.

The author's position in the case also requires clarification. The author is both the researcher and one of the participants: they coordinate the student circle, supervise the translations, and take part in communication with editors and authors. This creates a risk of partiality, but it also gives access to process data that would otherwise be difficult to observe. This limitation is addressed by grounding the analysis in public outcomes, by distinguishing description from interpretation, and by treating the case as situated practice rather than as a universal model.

4. Institutional setting and participants

The collaboration connects several institutions and groups. On the Ukrainian side, the educational setting is Mykhailo Dragomanov State University of Ukraine, especially the Department of Applied Linguistics and Translation Studies. The student research-and-practice circle *Practice of Written Translation in Action* provides the framework in which students work on translation projects beyond regular classroom assignments. The circle is designed to give students sustained experience of written translation, editing, revision, and publication.

On the German side, the partner is *Demokratischer Salon*, a German-language online magazine edited by literary scholar Norbert Reichel. The magazine defines itself as a space for historically and politically informed public reflection. Its website explicitly presents the Ukrainian translation initiative: selected texts from *Demokratischer Salon* are translated into Ukrainian by young Germanists at Dragomanov University in Kyiv under the guidance of the supervisor, and these translations are usually published in *Experiment* and *Krytyka* (Reichel n.d.). The same page also notes the reciprocal direction: *Demokratischer Salon* publishes texts by Ukrainian authors, including reviews of Ukrainian theater productions and background materials useful for understanding the country.

Ukrainian media partners play an equally important role. *Experiment*, edited by Herman Hoshkador, is a cultural portal and has become the main publication venue for the Ukrainian translations from *Demokratischer Salon*. *Krytyka*, with editors including Iuliia Bentia and Bohdana Matiyash, is a Ukrainian intellectual journal. It published the first translation in the collaboration and has also permitted *Demokratischer Salon* to translate and publish some of its Ukrainian-language texts in German. *Syg.ma*, a multilingual community-run media platform and translocal archive, published one translation connected with Russian émigré culture in Germany. This publication choice was deliberate: because the text was less directly connected with immediate Ukrainian public debates, *Syg.ma* offered a suitable way to reach Ukrainian-reading audiences within a broader

multilingual intellectual space. These platforms give the student translations a readership and place them in the public sphere. They also introduce students to editorial standards, publication schedules, formatting requirements, title choices, and the expectations of online audiences.

The participants in the collaboration, therefore, include student translators, the supervisor, editors of Ukrainian media, authors of the German-language source texts, Norbert Reichel as editor of *Demokratischer Salon*, and readers. The partnership should be seen as a translation ecology rather than a linear transfer from one text to another. Each participant contributes to the final publication. Students draft and revise; the supervisor coordinates and edits; Ukrainian editors decide whether and how the texts fit their platforms; German authors and the German editor provide permission, context, and sometimes feedback; readers complete the process by reading, sharing, and responding.

This ecology is particularly significant because the translators are German Studies students in wartime Ukraine. Their work connects language learning with civic and cultural needs. German becomes both an object of study and a medium through which students gain access to debates on democracy, authoritarianism, gender, pedagogy, literature, history, war, and memory. Ukrainian, in turn, gives these debates a new public setting and renewed relevance for local readers.

5. Workflow: From text selection to publication

The workflow usually begins with the selection of a socially, politically, or culturally relevant text. Selection may be proposed by the supervisor, suggested by students, or arise from ongoing communication with *Demokratischer Salon*. The chosen texts tend to be long-form essays, interviews, or reviews that can be valuable for Ukrainian readers. Relevance is not understood narrowly. Some texts deal directly with war, peace, or democracy; others approach public life through literature, science fiction, art, music, pedagogy, or cultural memory.

After a text is selected, students prepare a draft translation. Depending on the length and difficulty of the source text, the project may be assigned to one student, a small group, or a larger class group. Collaborative translation is especially useful for long interviews and essays because it gives students experience of coordination and consistency. At this stage, they must research proper names, check references, understand allusions, identify terms that require contextual adaptation, and produce Ukrainian prose suitable for publication.

The next stage is collective discussion and revision. Drafts are reviewed by the supervisor and, in some projects, by other students. Comments usually address semantic accuracy, Ukrainian style, terminological consistency, factual precision, genre conventions, and cultural intelligibility. Several translation problems were especially instructive because they required students to combine linguistic accuracy, cultural

knowledge, and sensitivity to the Ukrainian public sphere. In the translation of Norbert Reichel's interview with Aiki Mira, for example, the translators used plural first-person past-tense verb forms in Ukrainian when Aiki Mira spoke about themselves. This solution was chosen because Ukrainian past tense verbs mark gender in the singular, whereas the plural form avoids assigning a binary gender to a non-binary author. In another case, when translating the German word *Dystopie*, the group chose the Ukrainian term *antyutopiia* because it appeared to be the more established convention in Ukrainian critical usage. These examples show that revision involves discussion of grammar, identity, terminology, genre, and target-culture norms.

Other problems concerned factual precision and the political framing of war. In the translation of Fritz Heidorn's essay on Carl Sagan, the translators noticed that the source text identified I. S. Shklovsky as a Russian astronomer. In the Ukrainian translation, this was corrected to "Ukrainian Soviet astrophysicist of Jewish descent," a formulation that more accurately reflected his biography. Similar discussions arose around references to the war. German formulations such as *Ukraine-Krieg* or *Krieg in der Ukraine* were regularly rendered as *rosiisko-ukrainska viina* [Russo-Ukrainian War] in Ukrainian, because the Ukrainian formulation explicitly names Russia as the aggressor and avoids presenting the war as a geographically neutral conflict "in Ukraine."

When necessary, the supervisor communicates with editors or authors. This may involve obtaining permission, clarifying publication details,

checking names, or asking about ambiguous formulations. The final Ukrainian version is then sent to the relevant publication venue. The editors may make further changes, ask for corrections, or adjust the text to the platform's style. The publication itself is an important learning moment because students see how their translation is framed by titles, images, tags, introductory notes, and editorial formatting.

This workflow teaches research skills, stylistic responsibility, fact-checking, teamwork, and openness to editorial revision. It also teaches students to accept that translation is not completed in isolation. A publishable text is the result of many decisions made across several stages. Students learn that professional translation requires both confidence and humility: they must take responsibility for their choices, while accepting that editors and the supervisor can improve the final text.

6. The first example: Translating Stanislav Aseyev through Ursula Stark Urrestarazu

The collaboration began with the Ukrainian translation of Ursula Stark Urrestarazu's review of Stanislav Aseyev's *Heller Weg: Geschichte eines Konzentrationslagers im Donbass 2017–2019*, the German translation of his book about Izolyatsia, the torture prison in occupied Donetsk (Stark Urrestarazu 2023a). The Ukrainian translation, titled “Za mezheiu liudianosti” [Beyond humanity], was translated from German by Viktoriia

Penkovska, Yana Poltorak, and Karyna Khomenko and published in *Krytyka* in March 2023 (Stark Urrestarazu 2023b).

This first example is important for several reasons. First, the source text concerned a Ukrainian author and a Ukrainian experience of war, violence, and captivity, but it reached Ukrainian readers through a German-language review. The translation therefore created a complex circuit: a Ukrainian testimony was translated into German, reviewed in a German-language venue, and then reintroduced into Ukrainian public discourse through student translation. Such indirect circulation might appear unnecessary at first glance, because the original Ukrainian book already existed. Yet the German review offered an external reading of Aseyev's testimony and showed how the book was received in a German-speaking intellectual context. Ukrainian translation made that reception visible to Ukrainian readers.

Second, the project created direct human connections. The author of the review welcomed the Ukrainian translation, and Aseyev (2023) publicly thanked Stark Urrestarazu and those involved in translating her work. This response showed students that translation can connect authors, translators, editors, and readers in ways that classroom exercises rarely do. Their work was noticed by the people most closely connected with the subject matter.

Third, the project established trust among the partners. The translation required permission and coordination with *Demokratischer Salon* and with the author of the review. After this successful first project, Norbert Reichel

allowed students to translate other texts from the magazine. This was the beginning of a broader collaboration, and it shows how a single translation can become the foundation for a sustained institutional relationship.

7. The corpus: Genres, themes, and public value

The 33 Ukrainian translations from *Demokratischer Salon* form a varied corpus of long-form public writing. Some texts are closely connected with the Russo-Ukrainian War, peace politics, violence, and European security, including Markus Meckel's speech on peace ethics during the Russo-Ukrainian War, Norbert Reichel's review of Sofi Oksanen's book on Putin's war against women, Paul Schäfer's analysis of peace politics after the *Zeitenwende*, and Meckel's later reflection on the Polish memorial in Berlin (Meckel 2024, 2025b; Reichel 2024b; Schäfer 2024). Others address authoritarianism, liberal ethics, democracy, law, local self-government, constitutional crisis, and asylum debates in Germany and Europe (Hänel 2026; Meckel 2025a; Reichel 2024a, 2025a, 2025c; Winkler 2025). A further group deals with pedagogy, childhood, history, and memory, including diversity in German educational life, the politics of childhood, historical-political discourse with Christina Morina, women in divided Germany, and the memory of East Germany (Marz 2025; Reichel 2024c; Reichel and Morina 2024; Reichel 2025b).

Another group of texts opens cultural, literary, and popular-science fields to Ukrainian readers. Interviews with Dilek Güngör and Aiki Mira

introduce questions of literature, identity, queer poetics, and science fiction (Reichel 2024d, 2024e). Texts by Fritz Heidorn, Alessandra Reß, Karlheinz Steinmüller, Zara Zerbe, Norbert Reichel, and Corinna Heumann discuss immortality, climate dystopia, solarpunk, artificial intelligence, Arthur C. Clarke, Carl Sagan, realistic speculative fiction, censored science fiction in East Germany, and Atwoodian utopias (Heidorn 2024a, 2024b, 2025a, 2025b, 2025c; Heumann 2025; Reß 2024; Steinmüller 2025; Zerbe and Reichel 2025). Other translations address art, body, storytelling, music, cultural projects, Georgian-German exchange, Soviet Tbilisi, and Russian émigré culture in Germany (Heidorn 2025d, 2025e; Margvelashvili 2026a, 2026b; Reichel 2024f, 2025d, 2025e).

Essays require students to follow argumentation, rhetoric, and style. Interviews require them to preserve voices, conversational flow, and pragmatic nuance. Reviews require attention to evaluative language, contextual information, and cultural references. Popular-science and cultural-historical texts require research and terminological precision. This variety gives students experience with non-literary translation, a field that is central to public discourse but often less visible in traditional literary models of translator education.

The corpus also shows the educational value of translation beyond the classroom. Ukrainian readers gain access to German-language discussions on topics that are relevant to Ukraine but not always available in Ukrainian. These translations broaden the range of voices in Ukrainian public debate.

They also show students that a translated text on democracy, education, asylum, or historical memory can contribute to the intellectual environment in which readers think about public life. Visible readership figures on Ukrainian platforms confirm that at least some of these texts reached audiences far beyond the immediate student group.

8. Educational effects: From classroom work to professional agency

The educational value of the collaboration lies in the movement from simulated translation to public responsibility. In ordinary classroom translation, the main audience is the teacher. The student may try to meet assessment criteria, but the translation usually has no life beyond the classroom. In this project, the final text is published. It can be read, shared, criticized, cited, and archived. This changes the student's relationship to the task.

First, students learn professional responsibility. They know that inaccuracies, awkward phrasing, or insufficient research may reach readers beyond the classroom. This increases the importance of careful revision. Students must check facts, verify names, compare contexts, and think about how a Ukrainian reader will understand the text. Student reflections from one documented mini-project confirm this point. In a survey conducted after the collaborative translation of Fritz Heidorn's essay on climate dystopia, students reported that peer review helped them notice their own mistakes, understand linguistic nuances, compare different translation strategies, and

search for more precise equivalents (Shopin 2025d). One student observed that analyzing classmates' translations improved her critical thinking and enriched her vocabulary because she had to look for the right equivalents. Another emphasized that constructive criticism from the instructor and classmates helped her identify weak points and improve her translation skills. These comments show that responsibility emerged from the prospect of publication and from the process of reviewing, being reviewed, and revising with others.

Second, students develop professional agency. Their names appear in publications, either individually or collectively. This gives them a public record of translation work and helps them see themselves as participants in a professional community. Public credit is pedagogically important because it counters the invisibility of translation labor. It also motivates students: publication becomes a form of recognition.

The earlier mini-project on Heidorn's essay also shows that publication changes how students understand the task. Three students reported that they had completed the project fully, while three described completion as only partial because the final editing and publication took place after the class. This response is revealing: students did not treat the classroom translation as complete once their own fragment had been translated. They understood the task as a longer process that included revision, editorial preparation, and publication. In this sense, delayed publication was part of professional learning, because it helped students see translation as a staged

process involving several participants and extending beyond the lesson itself (Shopin 2025d).

Third, students learn collaboration. Many projects are collective. Students must divide work, harmonize terminology, review one another's parts, and accept feedback. These skills are essential in professional translation environments, where translators often work with editors, project managers, authors, and other translators. In the documented mini-project, five of six respondents considered peer collaboration useful, while one considered it partially useful. Their comments suggest that peer review helped them compare translation approaches, develop metalinguistic reflection, and learn to justify their choices. One student noted that discussing different translation options taught the group to collaborate effectively, express opinions, and argue their point of view, which she considered useful for future professional activity (Shopin 2025d). The collaboration therefore creates a community of practice in Wenger's (1998) sense: students learn by participating in shared work oriented toward a meaningful outcome.

Fourth, students encounter editorial culture. Ukrainian editors have their own expectations concerning titles, introductions, style, spelling, typography, political sensitivity, and audience orientation. The first translation in the collaboration, Ursula Stark Urrestarazu's review of Stanislav Aseyev's book, was substantially edited at *Krytyka* by the literary editor Bohdana Matiyash. Dozens of changes were introduced before publication, and this made the students' first public translation a direct

encounter with professional literary editing. The situation at *Experiment* is different: editorial intervention there is usually minimal, but editorial preferences still matter. One revealing example concerns the wartime Ukrainian tendency to write “russia” and “putin” with lowercase letters. Students sometimes followed this convention; the supervisor usually corrected such forms according to standard orthographic practice, while *Experiment* editors sometimes restored the lowercase forms. *Krytyka*, by contrast, did not follow this trend. Such cases teach students that editorial culture includes different views of political typography, institutional style, and standardization.

Finally, the project supports civic education. The texts translated from Demokratischer Salon deal with questions that matter for democratic life: authoritarianism, violence, peace, childhood, law, education, memory, gender, ecology, and culture. Translating such texts requires students to understand public arguments and render them responsibly. The documented mini-project on climate dystopia is one example: students chose the text themselves from several options, worked on a topic connecting ecology and literature, and knew that the translation would appear in Ukrainian media. This combination of choice, public audience, and topical relevance helped make translation a form of intercultural communication rather than a purely linguistic exercise (Shopin 2025d). In this sense, translator education becomes part of a broader process of civic learning.

9. Reciprocity: Ukrainian debates for German-speaking readers

While students translate German-language texts into Ukrainian, *Demokratischer Salon* also publishes texts connected with Ukraine for German-speaking readers. This reciprocal direction is crucial because it prevents the collaboration from becoming a simple import of German-language debates into Ukraine. Instead, it creates a two-way circulation of ideas.

One major area is Ukrainian theater. *Demokratischer Salon* has published texts and conversations about *Coriolanus* in Ukraine, Shakespeare's *A Midsummer Night's Dream* in Kyiv, Ukrainian theater during the war, Poulenc's *Dialogues of the Carmelites* at the Lviv Opera, dramatherapy in wartime Ukraine, and the history of Ukrainian theater. These texts present Ukrainian performance culture as intellectually rich and politically significant. They also help German-speaking readers encounter Ukraine beyond news images of destruction and military conflict.

Another area is Ukrainian history, literature, and cultural memory. *Demokratischer Salon* has published texts by or about Mykola Riabchuk, Jeonghun Choi, Volodymyr Krizhanovskyj, Yaroslav Hrytsak, Alois Woldan, Alla Paslawska, and others. The topics include Central Europe, Ukrainian history in Japan, Kafka in Ukraine, Galicia, Ivan Mazepa, the beginning of the Russo-Ukrainian War in Donbas, and German Studies in Ukraine. These publications contribute to a German-language understanding of Ukraine as a complex cultural and historical space.

The supervisor's own German translations and self-translation in *Demokratischer Salon* add another layer to this reciprocal circulation. Between October 2025 and February 2026, seven German-language texts appeared there. These included the supervisor's self-translation of an article on intercultural learning through Ukrainian performances of German-language works (Shopin 2025a); their German translation of Yuliia Dobronosova's review of a major study of Ukrainian theater culture (Dobronosova 2025); their translation of Mykhailo Liakh's article on Lesia Ukrainka's political life between Drahomanov and Marx (Liakh 2025); three translations of Lesia Smyrna's essays on post-Bucha reflections on tenderness, Maria Kulikovska, and Yana Kononova (Smyrna 2025, 2026a, 2026b); and their translation of Mykola Riabchuk's essay on Ukrainian self-awareness and "Ukraine fatigue" (Riabchuk 2026).

These texts are relevant to the student translation project because they show that the partnership is embedded in a broader Ukrainian-German cultural exchange. Student translations into Ukrainian and German-language texts about Ukraine are two sides of one process. Together they create a shared space in which Ukrainian and German-speaking publics can encounter one another through essays, interviews, reviews, and cultural criticism.

10. Translation as community-building

The collaboration with *Demokratischer Salon* builds community on several levels. At the most immediate level, it creates a student community. Students

work together, revise one another's texts, share responsibility, and see their translations published. This strengthens their sense of belonging to a group with a common purpose.

At the professional level, the collaboration connects students with editors and authors. Such contact is valuable because it demystifies publication. Students learn that authors can be approachable, editors can be supportive, and translation can begin a conversation. The first Aseyev-related translation is a clear example: the students' work connected them with a German author, a Ukrainian intellectual magazine, and the Ukrainian author whose work had been reviewed. This pattern continued in later projects. Norbert Reichel regularly shared Ukrainian student translations with the authors of the German source texts, and authors often thanked the students or sent personal responses. Such exchanges are modest but important traces of reception: they show that student translation did not disappear into an anonymous online archive but returned to the authors as a visible act of intercultural mediation.

At the media level, the collaboration builds trust between outlets. *Demokratischer Salon* trusts the Ukrainian translation group to work responsibly with its texts. Ukrainian media trust the student translations enough to publish them. This trust has been built through repeated successful projects. It is fragile and must be maintained through quality, reliability, and ethical communication. Although audience reception is difficult to measure

directly, repeated publication in trusted venues creates conditions in which translated texts can enter public circulation with institutional credibility.

At the public level, the translations create possible communities of readers. Online publication allows texts to circulate through social media, newsletters, search engines, and personal recommendations. This understanding of reception builds on previous work on popular-text translation in educational practice, where comments, social-media circulation, reader discussions, and platform analytics were treated as partial indicators of translation's public life (Shopin 2025b). Some traces of this circulation are visible. *Krytyka*, *Experiment*, and *Syg.ma* display reader statistics, unlike *Demokratischer Salon*, which does not provide a public view counter. Stark Urrestarazu's Aseyev-related review in Ukrainian reached more than two thousand unique views on *Krytyka*, according to the platform's counter. Reichel and Morina's historical-political interview with Christina Morina had 1,874 views on *Experiment* as of 24 May 2026, while the *Syg.ma* publication on Russian émigré culture in Germany displayed 1.2K views and appeared as a popular publication on the platform. The supervisor also shared student translations in relevant Facebook groups, including groups for Ukrainian academics and historians, where they received visible likes, comments, and shares. These numbers and reactions do not provide a complete picture of reception, but they show that the translations reached readers beyond the classroom and entered specialized online communities.

This community-building function is especially important under wartime conditions. War can isolate publics and harden stereotypes. Translation can counteract that tendency by giving readers access to more complex voices. It can also sustain solidarity without simplifying differences. The partnership discussed here brings into contact many authors, topics, and viewpoints. This plurality is one of its strengths.

11. Discussion: A model of publication-oriented student translation

The case suggests a model of publication-oriented student translation built around five components.

The first component is institutional anchoring. The project requires a stable educational setting, in this case the student circle at Dragomanov University, and a stable media partner, in this case *Demokratischer Salon*. Without institutional continuity, individual translations might remain isolated events.

The second component is editorial trust. Students need access to publication venues, but media outlets need confidence that translations will meet professional standards. The supervisor plays a mediating role by coordinating quality control, communication, and revision.

The third component is socially meaningful text selection. The texts should matter to readers. Although the Russo-Ukrainian War is central to public discourse in Ukraine, texts on science fiction, childhood, music, or

pedagogy can also contribute to public life. They bring new knowledge, perspectives, and debates into the target culture.

The fourth component is collaborative revision. Publication-oriented translation requires multiple rounds of feedback. Revision should be treated as learning rather than as correction alone. Students need to understand why changes are made and how translation choices affect meaning, style, and reception. Preserved draft documents and published versions can later become teaching and research material because they show how translation problems were identified, discussed, corrected, or deliberately retained.

The fifth component is public attribution and archiving. Students should be credited for their work, and translations should be publicly accessible. This creates professional recognition and allows the corpus to become a resource for later research, teaching, and reflection.

The model has limitations. It depends on motivated students, supportive editors, available texts, permissions, and the supervisor's labor. Student reflection from one documented mini-project also shows that participation may be uneven and that online collaboration can limit spontaneous interaction, especially when students' active command of German is still developing (Shopin 2025d). The model also raises ethical questions. Student work must not be exploited as unpaid content production. The educational value of the project must remain central, and students should understand the publication process clearly. They should also have opportunities to decline participation or remain outside public credit if

necessary. Another limitation concerns reception. Public circulation can be observed through platform counters, author responses, comments, social-media reactions, shares, and citations, but such indicators do not fully measure impact. View counts do not show how carefully a text was read, social-media reactions may be uneven or platform-dependent, and private responses cannot always be quoted. A translation may also influence readers in ways that leave no visible trace.

Despite these limitations, the case shows that publication-oriented translation can bridge the gap between translator education and professional practice. It gives students authentic tasks, real audiences, and meaningful feedback. It also supports media cooperation across borders. Under wartime conditions, this cooperation acquires civic significance because it helps maintain channels of dialogue between Ukrainian and German-speaking publics.

12. Conclusion

The collaboration between *Demokratischer Salon* and Ukrainian student translators at Mykhailo Dragomanov State University of Ukraine demonstrates how translation can function as professional training, civic education, intercultural dialogue, and community-building. The project began with one Ukrainian translation of a German review connected with Stanislav Aseyev's testimony about Izolyatsia. It developed into a sustained partnership that has produced dozens of long-form Ukrainian translations of German-

language essays and interviews, and has also supported the circulation of Ukrainian cultural and intellectual debates in German.

For students, the project offers experience that cannot be fully reproduced through classroom exercises. They translate texts selected for publication, respond to editorial feedback, and write for readers beyond the university setting. They learn to research, revise, collaborate, and take responsibility for published work. They also gain a sense of belonging to a professional community. For media partners, the project expands the reach of socially relevant content. For readers, it opens access to debates across linguistic and cultural borders.

The case contributes to Translation Studies by showing how translator training, public discourse, and intercultural cooperation can be integrated in a concrete long-term practice. It supports the view that translation is a situated cultural activity shaped by institutions, communities, and ethical choices. It also suggests that student translation projects can become sustainable forms of public scholarship and civic engagement when they are based on trust, editorial cooperation, public attribution, and shared responsibility.

In wartime Ukraine, such work has particular importance. Translation can keep intellectual and cultural channels open. It can help readers understand one another across borders and support solidarity between a society under attack and international audiences. Most importantly for translator education, it can show students that their developing skills already matter in the world beyond the classroom.

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